

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF TEST METHODS FOR THE DETERMINATION OF THROUGH-THICKNESS PROPERTIES INTENSION, COMPRESSION AND SHEAR OF LONG FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The detailed design of 3D laminated structures has shown the need for reliable methods for measuring the through-thickness mechanical properties of composite materials. In this work, finite element studies have been conducted in order to develop suitable test methods for the determination of the through-thickness strengths and elastic constants in tension, compression and shear. For these three loading cases, the specimens are loaded directly either normally or in shear. In both cases of direct normal and shear loading, two specimen designs are proposed: a parallel-sided block for the determination of the elastic constants only and an elliptically-waisted specimen for the determination of both the elastic constants and strength.

KEYWORDS: through-thickness, mechanical properties, test method, finite element, shear, tension, compression

INTRODUCTION

The structural design of laminated components is largely dependent on the accurate input of the material mechanical properties in tension, compression and shear. Standardised test methods exist for the evaluation of most of the in-plane elastic constants and strength parameters. As long as the design approach remains two-dimensional, this is sufficient. However, structures have become more complex 3D arrangements for the design of which the through-thickness (TT) material mechanical properties are also required. No recognised standards exist for TT tension or compression testing. So far as shear is concerned, the Iosipescu test technique [1] has out-of-plane possibilities [2,3] but, in that case, the determination of the shear strength is erroneous since failure is more due to transverse tension than to shear [4].

Numerous attempts at developing suitable TT test methods have been undertaken and these have been reviewed elsewhere [5-7]. A suitable TT test method should make use of simple specimens cut from laminates which are not too thick (thick laminates being difficult to manufacture), ensure a pure and uniform stress state in the gauge section which leads to the expected failure mode, rely on a direct and simple analysis and enable the determination of

both elastic and strength parameters. Based on an extensive literature search [5], the most promising methods have been short listed. These have been studied with finite element (FE) methods for optimisation and tested experimentally for complete validation. The experimental results from tensile [8] and compressive [9] testing have already been reported. The present article reports the results of the FE study for the investigated test methods. These are the direct normal test method which has tensile and compressive possibilities and the direct shear test method.

PRELIMINARY CONSIDERATIONS

Material Properties

The material properties used for the FE analysis are reported in table 1. They are those of Hexcel carbon/epoxy T300/914. The in-plane properties were determined by in-plane testing and, for these, the coefficients of variation are given in brackets in the table. The determination of the other properties is based on the assumption of material transverse isotropy. All the FE analyses were conducted on unidirectional (UD) material.

Table 1: Mechanical properties data for FE input (UD Carbon/Epoxy T300/914)

Elastic Properties		Strength Properties (MPa)	
E_1 (GPa)	129 (3.3%)	σ_{1t}^u	1434 (7.6%)
E_2 (GPa)	9.5 (1.6%)	σ_{1c}^u	1318 (7%)
E_3 (GPa)	9.5	σ_{2t}^u	48 (8.3%)
G_{12} (GPa)	4.7 (1.3%)	σ_{2c}^u	215 (9.1%)
G_{23} (GPa)	3.2	σ_{3t}^u	48
G_{31} (GPa)	4.7	σ_{3c}^u	215
ν_{12}	0.34 (6.4%)	τ_{12}^u	79 (8%)
ν_{23}	0.5 ⁺	τ_{23}^u	79
ν_{13}	0.34	τ_{31}^u	79

⁺ Data from references [11,12]

Finite Element Study

The FE package used for this study is FE77, the in-house system of the Department of Aeronautics at Imperial College. All the analyses were performed in the linear elastic region. The 2D and 3D meshes were built up with 8-noded and 20-noded brick elements respectively with parabolic-shaped interpolation functions. Output average stresses were interpolated from the stresses at the Gauss points. The 3D Hill failure criterion was introduced into the code in order to locate the failure initiation.

DIRECT NORMAL TEST METHOD

Several authors have investigated this technique for TT parameters determination [2,10-13]. In this method, a normal (tensile or compressive) load is applied in the TT direction of the laminated specimen. There are several advantages to this method: simplicity of analysis, potential application to multi-directional laminates, determination of both elastic constants and strength parameters. Its main drawback though is the use of fairly long specimens which means that thick laminates have to be manufactured. The main objective of the FE analysis has therefore been to reduce as much as possible the specimen length while keeping a pure and uniform tensile or compressive stress state in the gauge section. Two specimen shapes have been investigated: the parallel-sided block and the waisted specimen.

Parallel-Sided Block

The 3D FE model used is represented in figure 1. Since there are 3 planes of symmetry, only 1/8 of the set-up needs to be meshed. The top surface of the model is completely constrained in the (xy) plane and a displacement of 0.1mm is applied in the TT z-direction. The end block material properties are those of aluminium ($E=72.4\text{GPa}$, $\nu=0.3$). The influence of the specimen length to width ratio (L/W) on the stress state purity and uniformity has been investigated.

Fig. 1: Parallel-sided block 3D FE model for normal testing

The TT normal stress σ_{33} (equivalent to σ_{zz}) is highest at the interface between the specimen and the jig. Failure will therefore always occur at this location but the geometry may still be suitable for elastic constants determination, provided a sufficiently uniform σ_{33} can be achieved over an appropriate gauge length. The results also showed, that although secondary stresses (σ_{11} , σ_{22} , σ_{31} and σ_{23}) are high at the interface, they decrease very rapidly away from it and become significantly lower than σ_{33} . The stress state can therefore be considered pure at a short distance from the interface.

The uniformity of the stress state can be quantified by the parameter $C_u(d)$ defined as follows:

$$C_u(d) = \frac{\sigma_{33}^{\min}}{\sigma_{33}^{\max}} \text{ on the (xy) plane at a distance } d \text{ from the interface (see fig. 1)}$$

with σ_{33}^{\min} and σ_{33}^{\max} being the minimum and maximum σ_{33} values respectively.

Figure 2 shows the curves $C_u(d)$ for different specimen dimensions. As can be seen in this figure, a good uniformity (i.e. $C_u > 0.9$) is obtained for specimen length to width ratios (L/W) of at least 2. In that case, $C_u = 0.9$ at $d = 1/3$ of L .

Further study for a laminated specimen attached to an epoxy end block ($E = 3\text{GPa}$ and $\nu = 0.3$) showed that the specimen length can be reduced to one specimen width and still achieve a C_u value of 0.9 at a distance $d = 1/3$ of L from the interface.

Waisted Specimen

As noted in the previous section, parallel-sided blocks fail at the bond line due to stress concentrations at this location. In order to avoid this problem, the specimen has to be waisted but the shape of the waisted section must be designed carefully so as to avoid significant stress concentrations at the transition to the gauge section (see location M in fig. 3). The design which proved the most successful for that purpose is an elliptically waisted specimen. The model is shown in figure 3. The parameter values are $a = 6\text{mm}$, $b = 2\text{mm}$, $c = 1\text{mm}$, $s = 4\text{mm}$ and $W = 4\text{mm}$.

Fig. 2: Stress uniformity in parallel-sided blocks attached to aluminium end block

Waisted specimen for direct normal testing

Fig. 3 (left and centre): 3D FE Model

Fig. 4 (right): Normalised σ_{33} contour plot

Figure 4 shows the normalised σ_{33} contour plot for this waisted specimen design (is carried out with regard to the average stress, σ_{33}^{av} , defined as the ratio of the reaction forces resultant to the cross-sectional area in the gauge section). The maximum occurs at M with σ_{33} at this location being 6% higher than σ_{33}^{av} . The Hill failure criterion is highest at the location of maximum σ_{33} with $\sigma_{33}/\sigma_{33}^u$, being the dominant term by far (σ_{33}^u is the composite tensile or compressive strength). This implies an essentially pure TT normal stress failure, i.e. the other stresses do not contribute to failure. The value of σ_{33} at the interface is approximately half the value in the gauge section. Provided the bond strength between the loading bar and the specimen is high enough, the failure will therefore occur within the specimen in pure tension or compression.

The influence of variations in the semi-major axis, a , of the elliptical waisting on the stress concentration at location M and at the interface has been investigated (leaving all the other parameters constant at the values given above). For that purpose, the stress concentration parameter C_c is introduced:

$$C_c = \frac{\sigma_{33}^{max}}{\sigma_{33}^{av}} \quad \text{with } \sigma_{33}^{max} \text{ the maximum TT normal stress at M or at the interface}$$

Figure 5 shows the results of this study.

Fig. 5: Stress concentrations at location M and at the interface in waisted specimens

From these curves, it is clear that the σ_{33} concentrations decrease with increasing values of a . With a circular fillet ($a=b=4\text{mm}$), the stress concentrations at location M are 12% higher than the average stress. It is therefore advisable to use an elliptically shaped specimen.

A major subject of concern when devising a direct normal test method for strength determination is that of load misalignment. A simple calculation based on beam bending theory shows that a misalignment as low as $1/60$ of the width, W , between the specimen and the load axes induces bending stresses on the outer face which amount to 10% of the average stress. This result has been confirmed numerically. The interested reader is invited to consult references [8,9] for the experimental applications of the present numerical study.

DIRECT SHEAR TEST METHOD

The principle of this method is shown in figure 6 where both the specimen (simple parallel-sided block) and the steel jig are represented (steel properties: $E=207\text{GPa}$, $\nu=0.3$). The load axis coincides with the specimen axis so that no overall bending stresses are induced. Two orientations of the composite UD material have been used: type 'x' with the fibres in the x direction and type 'z' with the fibres in the z direction for the determination of the (31) and (32) properties respectively. Moreover, as for the direct normal test method, two designs have been investigated: the parallel-sided block and the waisted specimen. All the analyses in this section are two-dimensional.

Parallel-Sided Block

The objective here is to ensure that the measured strain at the centre of the specimen edge (point O, Fig. 6) is equal to the average strain so that the shear modulus can be measured accurately. For this study, the parameter C_0 has been introduced. It is defined as follows:

$$C_0 = \frac{\tau_{31}^0}{\tau_{31}^{\text{av}}} \quad \text{with } \tau_{31}^0 \text{ the shear stress at point O and } \tau_{31}^{\text{av}} \text{ the average shear stress}$$

τ_{31}^{av} is defined as the ratio of the reaction forces resultant to the specimen cross-sectional area in the plane (xz). Suffix i takes the value 1 for type 'x' and 2 for type 'z' specimens.

First, let us take the simple case of a block, made of type (x) material, at the top surface of which a uniform displacement of 0.1 mm is applied in the x-direction, as shown on the left of figure 7. In the same figure, the curve on the right shows the variation of the parameter C_0 with the ratio L/H . When this ratio is higher than 10, C_0 is close to 1 and the shear modulus could therefore be determined accurately.

Fig. 6: Parallel-sided block 2D FE model for direct shear testing

Fig. 7: C_0 in type 'x' specimens of varying length subjected to uniform displacement

In practice however, the specimen will not be attached to an infinitely rigid material but to an elastic material. The edges will therefore be subjected to higher stresses than the middle. Figure 6 showed the model which accounts for this real situation. In this case, the specimen length, L , and height, H , and the jig thickness, T , all influence the shear stress distribution in the specimen. When L and T are kept constant, the shear stress uniformity along $[AB]$ (see figure 6) increases with increasing values of H and C_0 converges towards 1. For practical purposes, H was taken to be 8mm. This thickness enables strain gauges to be bonded at the centre of the specimen edge while keeping the laminate thickness from which the specimen will be cut relatively low. In this case, the influence of T and L on C_0 was investigated. The results of this study are shown in figure 8. As clearly seen on this graph, the higher the L/T ratio, the closer C_0 is to its converging value which is itself very close to the value calculated

in the simple case of figure 7. For relatively long specimens (80mm and over), an acceptable level of stress uniformity (i.e. $C_0=0.95$) is reached for high values of T (50mm and over). Practically, the steel jig thickness, T , should not be higher than 20mm for handling purposes. Therefore, shorter specimens have to be used.

Fig. 8: Left, C_0 in type 'x' specimens attached to jig; and right, normalised shear stress distribution along the horizontal mid line [AB] of the specimen

On the right of figure 8, two characteristic shear stress distribution curves are shown for $L=20$ mm. When $T=20$ mm (top curve), the shear stress curve is a plateau whereas when $T=2$ mm (bottom curve), the maximum shear stress occurs at a short distance from the edges and then decreases to a minimum at point O. For the measurement of the shear modulus, the top curve shape is more satisfactory. However, in this case, the value of the shear stress in the plateau region is higher than the average stress, τ_{31}^{av} . This is due to the fact that the stress increases progressively from 0 at the edge to its maximum value over a distance, l , which is not negligible compared to L . After, the detailed analysis of 'plateau shaped' stress distribution curves for L varying from 20 to 30mm and $T=20$ mm, it has been found that l is constant and can be approximated to 4mm (when $L < 20$ mm, the curve has got a maximum at O but no plateau region). The modified average shear stress, $\tau_{31}^{av(mod)}$ can now be defined as $F/(L-l)$ for an out-of-plane width equal to unity. Table 2 compares the values of C_0 , calculated using τ_{31}^{av} and $C_0(mod)$, calculated using $\tau_{31}^{av(mod)}$ for 3 different specimen length. From these results, it is clear that the use of l in the calculation of $\tau_{31}^{av(mod)}$ to account for the stress gradient at the edges enables the use of the simple type 'x' parallel-sided specimens for G_{31} measurement.

Table 2: C_0 and $C_0(mod)$ for parallel-sided specimens attached to jig ($T=20mm$, $H=8mm$)

	Type 'x'	Specimens		Type 'z'	Specimens
	C_0	$C_0(mod)$		C_0	$C_0(mod)$
L=20mm	1.21	0.97		1.35	1.02
L=25mm	1.16	0.98	L=16mm	1.23	1.00
L=30mm	1.12	0.97			

The results for type 'z' material are similar. However, being less stiff in the loading direction, the 'plateau-shaped' shear stress distribution occurs only for specimens with a length lower than 16mm (and higher than 12mm) and the length l is equal to 3mm. The values of C_0 and $C_0(mod)$ are given in table 2. Here again, $C_0(mod)$ gives better results. Provided l can be estimated, the parallel-sided specimen provides therefore with an accurate measurement of G_{23} .

Waisted Specimen

The previous parallel-sided specimens fail at the corners where very high stress concentrations occur. It is necessary to reduce the specimen cross-section in the middle so as to avoid this phenomenon and achieve failure within the specimen. This will occur if the specimen is waisted as shown in figure 9. However, two other problems have to be tackled. Firstly, the shear stress concentrations in the region of high curvature are high. Secondly, the transverse tensile stress is still significant. The ratio of transverse tensile to shear stress is indeed close to unity for this type of geometry. As the transverse tensile strength is lower than the shear strength (see table 1), the specimen is more likely to fail in tension than in shear.

In order to lower the shear stress concentrations and reduce the transverse tensile stress, epoxy end blocks have been added to the composite specimen as shown in figure 9. However, this is not sufficient to reduce the tensile stresses to an acceptable level. Therefore, a TT compressive load has been applied together with the longitudinal load in order to "close" the specimen and this has been achieved by applying a force F inclined to the axis of the specimen as shown in figure 9.

For the study of this model, a shear stress concentration coefficient, C_{3i} , and a transverse tensile stress coefficient, C_{33} , are introduced. They are defined as follows:

$$C_{3i} = \frac{\tau_{3i}^{max}}{\tau_{3i}^{av}} \quad \text{and} \quad C_{33} = \frac{\sigma_{33}^{max}}{\tau_{3i}^{av}}$$

with τ_{3i}^{max} and τ_{3i}^{av} , the maximum and average shear stress respectively, σ_{33}^{max} , the maximum TT tensile stress and suffix i takes the value 1 for type 'x' and 2 for type 'z' specimens. τ_{3i}^{av} is derived as follows:

$$\tau_{3i}^{av} = \frac{F_x}{W L_{eff}} \quad \text{with} \quad L_{eff} = L + 2e \frac{G_{ep}}{G_{3i}}$$

where F_x is the applied longitudinal force, W , the out-of-plane specimen width, L_{eff} , the effective length along x and G_{ep} , the epoxy shear modulus.

After a thorough investigation of the geometrical and loading parameters, an acceptable design was found to be as follows: $L=30\text{mm}$, $a=30\text{mm}$, $b=5\text{mm}$, $e=9\text{mm}$, $T=20\text{mm}$ and $\alpha=0.2$. In this case, $C_{31}=1.013$ and $C_{33}=0.401$. Figure 10 shows the normalised shear stress contour plot. τ_{31}^{max} occurs in the region labelled 'MAX', at the interface between the composite and the epoxy (after a convergence study was carried out, it was found that the value was not singular). σ_{33}^{max} also occurs at the interface between the composite and the epoxy.

The sensitivity of the model to the different parameters has been studied. Table 3 shows the effect of increasing separately parameters L , a , e and α by 10% on the stress coefficients C_{31} and C_{33} . The maximum variation of C_{31} and C_{33} is 2%. Clearly, the maximum shear and transverse tensile stresses are not too sensitive to minor changes in the geometry and loading conditions. The determination of τ_{31}^u should therefore be accurate provided the bond of the epoxy to the composite is stronger than the composite and this strength will not be too sensitive to experimental imprecision.

For the measurement of the shear strength τ_{32}^u , the reference model has been run with type (z) material. The output of the FE analysis is: $C_{32}=1.016$ and $C_{33}=0.279$. Compared to the type (x) specimen, the determination of the shear strength is as accurate (less than 2% error) and the maximum transverse tensile stress in the composite is 30% lower. This specimen is therefore suitable for the determination of τ_{32}^u .

Fig. 9: Waisted specimen 2D FE model for direct shear testing

Fig. 10: Normalised τ_{31} contour plot in the shear waisted specimen

Table 3: Sensitivity study of the waisted specimen under direct shear loading

	L	a	e	α	C31	C33
Reference	30	30	9	0.2	1.013	0.401
Increase L (+10%)	33	30	9	0.2	1.031 (+1.8%)	0.405 (+1%)
Increase a (+10%)	30	33	9	0.2	1.012 (-0.1%)	0.396 (-1.2%)
Increase e (+10%)	30	30	9.9	0.2	1.015 (+2%)	0.409 (+2%)
Increase α (+10%)	30	30	9	0.22	1.013 ($\pm 0\%$)	0.393 (-2%)

CONCLUSIONS

FE analysis has been used to design suitably shaped specimens for through-thickness compression, tension and shear testing for the determination of elastic constants and strength of unidirectional laminated carbon fibre reinforced epoxy (Hexcel T300/914). The compression and tension test method, called the "direct normal test method", involves a specimen under direct normal loading. Two specimen designs are proposed. Firstly, a parallel-sided block with a square cross-section which allows only the determination of the elastic constants. Its length to width ratio depends on the material to which it is attached. If attached to a stiff material (e.g. aluminium), this ratio is 2. If attached to a soft material (e.g. epoxy), the ratio can be reduced to 1. Secondly, a waisted specimen design is proposed, allowing the measurement of both the elastic constants and the strength. It has a central gauge section of 4mm square cross-section widening to 8mm square at the ends via elliptically shaped fillets. Its total length is 16mm.

The shear test method, called the "direct shear test method", involves a specimen under direct shear loading. Only a 2D FE analysis has been carried out. Two specimen designs are again proposed. Firstly, as for the direct normal test method, a parallel-sided block specimen has been developed. It allows the determination of the shear moduli, provided the area under stress is corrected to account for stress gradients occurring at the specimen edges. The specimen thickness is 8mm while its length depends on the laminate orientation. For specimens with fibres in the loading direction, the length is between 20 and 30mm whereas for specimens with fibres normal to the loading direction, it is comprised between 12 and 16mm. Secondly, a waisted specimen is proposed for the determination of the shear strength (τ_{31}^u and τ_{32}^u). In order to minimise the shear stress concentrations and the transverse tensile stress, the design makes use of epoxy end blocks. Moreover, the loading involves a closing force, normal to the specimen longitudinal axis.

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